

THE ROLE OF DOCUMENTATION AND DIGITALIZATION IN WALL PAINTING CONSERVATION: ADDRESSING FALLEN OR DETACHED PAINTINGS

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ABSTRACT

Documentation of wall paintings is essential for studying, inspecting, and monitoring monuments in conservation. This non-invasive approach is increasingly valuable for preserving cultural heritage. Technological advancements in digitization offer innovative solutions for systematically documenting movable and immovable heritage sites of significant historical importance.

This study focuses on wall paintings at risk of falling off or those that have already been detached. In these cases, combining established design techniques with modern digital technologies is crucial for preventing further damage and developing effective conservation strategies.

Methods such as 2D and 3D photography, digital modeling, and advanced imaging techniques play key roles in documentation. When damage is extensive, these tools are vital for capturing the artwork's original state and preserving its significance.

Recent disasters from armed conflicts and natural disasters underscore the need for innovative documentation techniques. Often, these digital methods are the only means to safeguard a monument's history, ensuring that the stories within these wall paintings endure for future generations.

Keywords: Digitalization of Cultural Heritage, Non-Invasive Investigations, Documentation Of Phenomena Of Wall Paintings, Detached And/Or Fallen Wall Paintings.

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INDRODUCTION

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In contemporary Georgian conservation practice and academic fields, as well as throughout the world, the integration of modern technologies and documentation methods into the research process of works of art and cultural heritage monuments is quite relevant and important. This topic is especially noteworthy in the direction of wall painting preservation.

The list of cultural heritage monuments of Georgia widely presents outstanding monuments of wall paintings from both the early (9th century) and the late period (19th century), which are mainly found in churches, although they are also common in secular buildings of the 19th-20th centuries. Therefore, in the process of studying the history of a monument and during its rehabilitation, it is necessary to consider not only the original materials and technology of the monument but also the results of historical or previous restoration interventions and alterations, which are often irreversible and constitute an integral part of the painting today. It is precisely the assessment of the above-mentioned characteristics and phenomena, the determination of the current state of the monument, its causes of damage and deterioration, and environmental conditions, that is the prerequisite for developing the correct conservation methodology. In the process of studying each monument, specialists need to include various research methods, which are being improved along with the development of technologies and allow researchers to obtain the most comprehensive information possible with minimal physical impact on the monument.

To discuss the current issues of the modern conservation and restoration school of wall painting in Georgia, it is important to briefly review the experience of the restoration school of the previous century, where we would like to focus special attention on one of the methods of restoration intervention, namely when the wall painting is detached from the original support – a wall (Mora et al., 1984; Bianca, 2022). It should be noted that the formation of the wall painting restoration school in Georgia began in the 20th century (approximately 1920-1930's), when, among various restoration interventions, in extreme cases, the method of detaching wall paintings was also used (Bakuradze, 1974). The main reason for removing paintings was their protection and survival, and from the very beginning, this intervention was considered an extreme form of restoration intervention, although the risks of the intervention and its negative consequences were less emphasized. There are many well-known examples of wall painting detachment/falling off in Georgia, including such prominent monuments as David Gareji (Buchukuri, 2000), Bertubani (Gagoshidze, 2013), Gelati Monastery, Zemo Krikhi (Potskhishvili et al., 2022-2023), etc. There is also a second reason, when, due to the poor condition of the wall painting, fragments of the painting naturally fell off. It is necessary to note clear differences between these events:

The term "detached wall painting" refers to fragments of wall paintings that have been deliberately separated from their original context, which may include the exterior and interior parts of the buildings.

The term “fallen wall paintings” refers to paintings that have incurred damage and have detached from their original context due to natural catastrophes, anthropogenic factors, or architectural conditions (Skhirtladze and Buchukuri, 2004; Collalucci, 2011).

As a result of both above-mentioned prerequisites, we obtain individual fragments of paintings removed from their original context, in an unstable state, and numerous obstacles arise in the direction of their future care, placement, and exhibition. Moreover, the number and scale of the fragments may include both small fragments (5-50 cm) and entire scenes of paintings removed from the interior of the church, the scale of which may reach several tens of meters. A clear example of such a case is the removed wall painting of the village of Likhauri (Guria, 15th - 16th centuries), 80% of which has been detached and is now presented in fragments (Figure 1). It includes a fragment of painting measuring tens of square meters, which is currently preserved in the laboratory of the Faculty of Restoration, Art History and Theory of the Tbilisi State Academy of Arts. However, there are many cases when most of such samples have not been properly studied to date, complete documentation is not found on them, and they are not properly maintained, moreover, in many cases, they are permanently damaged, or the process of deterioration is activated, and they are placed in inappropriate environmental conditions.

Figure 1. Fragment of the detached wall painting from the church of Likhauri (Guria), 2022. Tbilisi State Academy of Art. (© Gvantsa Potshishvili)

It should be noted that in the literature related to detached wall paintings, the focus is more on the removal process, the methodology, and the materials used in this process. And less is written about the transportation of the painting, its long-term conservation, or its presentation in the exhibition space. This is noted by the Danish author Isabelle Brajer (Brajer, 2002), who mainly

draws on Danish experience, although she cites several international examples and sources that will be of great help to the researcher interested in this direction. Briar also notes that there are many examples of removed wall paintings, in which documentation is insufficient or completely absent. Which, in turn, creates several other problems. The author named cases when fragments of paintings were exhibited in the wrong order. In addition, insufficient documentation/identification makes a sample worthless and, in some cases, even useless for research.

The detachment of wall paintings is practically no longer used in the modern field of conservation, as it is too aggressive and invasive (Lobell and Sorrentino, 2014), although the experience of the last century remains largely ignored in the Georgian conservation field. It seems that the results of the intervention have not yet been properly assessed and analyzed, as there is still no general information, a guide or a manual in Georgian language, on how to carry out initial emergency and long-term conservation measures on examples of fallen wall paintings that are discovered in the future (Figure 2). Also, what methodology should be used to remove, transport, transfer to new support, and exhibit wall paintings in cases where it is objectively impossible to preserve the wall paintings in their authentic context. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to initiate appropriate research in this direction, to complete documentation and inventory of existing fragments, which will lay the foundation for developing an appropriate methodology and long-term conservation plan for such examples.

Figure 2. Fallen fragments of the wall paintings in the Church of the Archangel in Tsvirmi, Mestia, Upper Svaneti, 2020. (©Gvantsa Potskhishvili)

THE IMPORTANCE AND ROLE OF DOCUMENTATION IN THE CONSERVATION PROCESS OF WALL PAINTINGS

About the given issue, the role of documentation and the modern digital world is of paramount

importance. High-quality documentation of such examples is the primary and most important stage of the process. Many years of experience have shown that documentation is of special and decisive importance in the field of conservation-restoration. Its production and compilation are considered an unconditional part of the code of "professional ethics" and are mandatory for all specialists (Bomin et al., 2014).

It can be said that recordings and documentation are the research methods, during which specialists carry out the initial identification and study of all the features of the monument. Accordingly, the documentation must be carried out and/or wall painting conservation specialists are involved in this process. The conservation process is an interdisciplinary field, where the expertise of specialists from different fields and their cooperation to obtain the desired result are important. However, it is fundamental that a wall painting conservation specialist directly participates in the process of research and the use of modern documentation methods, because it is precisely the process of compiling documentation and close observation that reveals the characteristics and peculiarities of the monument (Cather, 2006; Cather, 2010).

The importance of documentation has been emphasized since the 1950s. The Venice Charter emphasizes the importance of documentation: "Article 16: In all works of preservation, restoration or excavation, there should always be precise documentation in the form of analytical and critical reports, illustrated with drawings and photographs. Every stage of the work of clearing, consolidation, rearrangement and integration, as well as technical and formal features identified during the course of the work, should be included. This record should be placed in the archives of a public institution and made available to research workers. It is recommended that the report should be published" (ICOMOS, 1964).

The documentation process should run parallel to the work on the monument, from the beginning of the project to its completion, and should cover all stages of the work carried out. Documentation can be considered a language of communication between specialists, which simplifies relations, cooperation and collaboration with both colleagues and stakeholders.

It is important to define the purpose of documentation in the practice of wall painting conservation, as it is essential for investigating techniques and conditions, setting conservation priorities, planning interventions, monitoring long-term changes, facilitating communication with stakeholders, and creating archives for future reference.

The purpose of the documentation is to describe and demonstrate the condition of the cultural monument and its historical significance. To provide a visual and textual description of the monument at the beginning and after its completion. The purpose and methods of intervention on the monument should be described and justified. The intervention methodology and the date of the project should also be presented. In addition to the fact that the documentation should include research notes and types of intervention, it should also include recommendations for future care. This process involves systematic organization, sorting, and correcting information, easy access to existing data and its use during research, treatment and monitoring (Fiorillo et al., 2020).

It is important to define criteria for selection methods to ensure successful documentation, which may include but are not limited to methods that are safe for both conservators and paintings, precise, affordable, user-friendly, portable, and lightweight. Non-invasive techniques

that do not require sampling are the most suitable based on these criteria.

Within the framework of the above-mentioned ongoing research project (“Research on the problems related to the preservation of fallen and/or removed wall paintings and definition of the preservation methodology”, Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia, project: FR- 22- 2778), it is planned to document wall paintings detached from their original context, using non-invasive research methods (macro and micro imaging using incident and raking light, collection of inventory data, description of the condition and determination of needs). This work is necessary to start working on a database of detached and/or fallen wall paintings.

A brief description of methods includes:

- Regular imaging: Capturing images under visible incident and raking light to document surface details.
- Micro-imaging: Using a portable microscope to examine the paintings with high magnification. This method allows for detailed observation under incident, raking, and UV light (Figure 3).
- Graphical documentation: Mapping the types and distribution of the most significant deterioration phenomena.
- Visual (illustrated) glossary: Creating a glossary of defined terms for conditions, described and illustrated to ensure precision and consistency when referring to specific phenomena.
- As part of the research, a database will be created to document and organize the collected examples of detached wall painting fragments.

Figure 3. Process of examination of the paintings with high magnification using a portable microscope. (© Heritage Conservation Laboratory)

It was useful to obtain responses from colleagues from all around the world regarding these topics. The questionnaire developed as part of the research project was distributed to over 200 wall painting conservation specialists and art historians, including Georgian and foreign professionals, via direct outreach and social media, yielding 41 responses (16 from Georgia and 25 from abroad). It explored documentation methods during the detachment process and the availability of digital records. Most specialists reported using a combination of methods, such as written reports, photography, graphic documentation, and occasionally video recordings, though many noted that the documentation was done rather briefly.

PAST EXPERIENCE OF THE GEORGIAN CONSERVATION AND RESTORATION SCHOOL IN DOCUMENTING WALL PAINTINGS

It is noteworthy that the archive of the Georgian Restoration School is not enriched with restoration reports reflecting the work, which may include the purpose of the intervention, methodology, stages, and materials used. In most cases, this is a short report. Generally, the most informative are archival photographs, which are used to determine the condition of the wall painting and the chronology of the interventions and to identify the alleged interventions that are visible on the illustrations, although the scarcity of textual material is a major problem.

It is important to note that in describing the removal of wall paintings and subsequent works in Georgia, the authors of the articles inconsistently and incompletely convey the details of the removal of the paintings and the subsequent works. We also believe that the problem remains in the justification of the extreme necessity of removing the wall paintings, which, as a rule, is conveyed in one sentence and an affirmative form and does not consider either alternative methods or the negative aspects of removing the paintings. Moreover, all such cases are assessed by the restorers carrying out the works as successful interventions.

We would like to highlight a few examples where the need for documentation and the problems resulting from its scarcity are very clearly visible. One of the most striking examples of this is the wall painting of the Likhauri village church (15-16th centuries), the largest part of which has been removed from the wall, although there are no archival photographs or textural material and/or documentation depicting the process and methodology of the painting. As a result, the joining of fragments separated into small (2-15 cm.) pieces to make it possible to restore the image/scene is a very long and laborious task (Marsella and Garzia, 2018).

It is also important to focus on examples that have been damaged by natural disasters, such as earthquakes, or prolonged neglect and are currently stored in inappropriate and unsafe conditions, leading to their further damage and even loss.

CONCLUSIONS

We would like to draw attention to the importance of documentation and knowledge/mastery of modern technologies by wall painting professionals. They need to have access to basic tools and equipment, such as a camera, a handheld microscope, a computer, etc. It is necessary to

overcome the stigma that producing written and visual documentation is the responsibility of representatives of other fields, is difficult, and that a conservator cannot do it. It is necessary to create basic guidelines on the use of various documentation techniques and retrain personnel working in this field. In conservation professional circles, the scarcity of the use of modern technologies and the problems of correctly compiling documentation are still clear. In addition, in this direction, there is still no appropriate standard and a requirement for high-quality documentation from commissioning organizations. This process is especially important in terms of raising public awareness and disseminating information.

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